

dirty color led to prediction of heavy losses, but the spikelets later filled. The table shows GLD incidence on various cultivars.

Isolations on PDA from affected glumes and grains showed *C. lunata* (in

80% discolored grains) and *F. semitectum* (5%). Unlike in the 1978 wet season, *C. lunata* was prominent.

Inoculating *C. lunata* on emerged panicles by spraying and dipping, and on the boot stage by injecting spore or

mycelial suspensions on three dates produced symptoms of dirty panicle on almost all glumes and grains. *F. semitectum* did not produce discoloration by any of the tested inoculation procedures. ■

Survival of sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* at different soil depths

A. K. Roy, Regional Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu-782 460, Assam, India

Sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto — the rice sheath blight fungus — were grown on sterilized rice grain for 1½ months and then placed in a layer of 5, 10, and 15 cm deep soil respectively, in clay pots. On 17 August 1978, the pots were buried in a highland where the level of the soil of the pot and that of the field were the same. The soil in the pot contained 0.336% organic

carbon, 0.09% N, 57.3 kg available P₂O₅/ha, 1,111.5 kg available K₂O/ha and pH 6.95. The sclerotia with the soil mass from the different depths were taken out at monthly intervals, starting

Viability of sclerotia of *C. sasakii* buried at different soil depths (observation from 15 sclerotia), Assam, India.

Observation time (mo after start of study)	Viability of sclerotia (%) at soil depth of		
	5 cm	10cm	15 cm
3	1	1	2
4	1	1	1
6	1	1	2
7	2	2	2
8	1	2	1

at 3 months of burial, and retrieved by washing over a mesh. These were then surface-sterilized with mercuric chloride and viability was tested by growing them on potato dextrose agar mixed with streptomycin sulfate.

The table shows that the viability of sclerotia dropped considerably after 3 months (first observation) and remained almost the same, regardless of the depth of burial, up to 8 months (last observation). Sclerotia from the different soil depths were found to be colonized by different organisms including *Trichoderma viride*, but those retrieved from below 5 cm were colonized most and those from below 15 cm least. ■

Effect of seed treatment with fungicides in improving germination of sheath rot-infected seeds

V. Viswanathan and V. Mariappan, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

Sheath rot disease of rice caused by *Sarocladium attenuatum* Gams and Hawkworth caused grain discoloration of seeds in varieties ADT31, Bhavani, CO39, and CO40. In all four varieties, 45% of seeds died before emergence and seedlings that survived were about 30% (Table 1).

Six fungicides were tested for their efficiency in the control of seed germination failure. For each treatment 50 g seeds showing infection symptoms was

Table 1. Data on germination^a of 4 varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pre-emergence death (no.)	Post-emergence death (no.)	Seedlings that survived (no.)
ADT31	45	24	31
Bhavani	42	26	32
CO39	45	30	25
CO40	41	29	30

^aMean of 3 replications.

Table 2. Effect of fungicide seed treatment on germination. Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Germination ^a (%)	
	Immediately after seed treatment	After 6 mo storage
TMTD	60 (51)	47 (43)
Captan	72 (58)	56 (48)
Agrosan	66 (54)	52 (46)
Panoctine	75 (60)	67 (55)
Panoram	55 (48)	43 (41)
Benomyl	82 (65)	76 (61)
Control	44 (42)	24 (30)
SED	4.06	2.38
CD (P = 0.05)	8.72	(P = 0.05) 5.11

^aMean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

treated with fungicides at 2 g or 2 ml/kg seed. The seeds were then sown in pots containing 2 kg sterilized wetland soil. Untreated infected seeds were sown as the control. Another set of seeds treated with fungicides was stored in the laboratory at 25± 1°C for 6 months, then tested for germination 10 days after sowing.

Benomyl and panoctine improved seed germination best, both immediately after the treatment and after 6 months storage (Table 2). ■

Influence of diammonium phosphate on brown spot disease of rice

S. Kannaiyan, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur-602 025, Chingleput, Tamil Nadu, India

Brown spot of rice caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* is very severe at the seedling stage during *navarai* (Nov-Mar) and *thaladi* (Oct-Feb) seasons. A field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications during 1979 *navarai*. IR20, which is susceptible to brown leaf spot disease, was raised in a 5- x 2-m plot. Diammonium phosphate (DAP) was applied to the nursery and disease incidence was observed. The treatments were: 1) wet seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 10 hours; 2) sprouted seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 30 minutes; 3) basal dressing of 500 g DAP/10 m²; 4) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 7th day; 5) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 15th day; 6) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 7th day; 7) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 15th day; 8) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the